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The Social Persona Approach

Using Facebook to Illustrate User Groups

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Abstract

This paper presents the result of a survey conducted in collaboration between the project ACCEPT and the Geneva University Library. The objective was the evaluation of use and usefulness of the libraries' digital resources. To present the results, the survey responses were used to create "personas", fictional characters representing users' needs and actions. Personas are described on 1 or 2 pages including attitudes, goals, skills, as well as some fictional details to make the persona a more realistic character. For this last part, Facebook was used to find "personal" information to illustrate appropriately the different user groups and their corresponding needs.

1 Usability and usefulness in digital libraries

Evaluating digital libraries and electronic resources occupies information specialists since the first projects in the 1990's. The following three facets can be evaluated: system, content and user. The interaction framework (figure 1) of Tsakonas/Papatheodorou (2008, p. 1238) represents these features and their relationships: performance, usability and usefulness. This last point is the link between content and user and evaluates source relevance (how

does the content correspond topically to the task), document format (e.g. PDF, Word), resource reliability (or credibility), information level (e.g. full text, abstract, metadata) and coverage of the deposited documents (timelessness or degree of temporal coverage).

Figure 1: Interaction triptych Framework

In contrast to usability evaluation for which several established methods exist, analysing usefulness is slightly more difficult because there do exist no “standard methods” so far. However, there are two main approaches: evaluations based on attributes and evaluations based on questionnaires.

The first one consists of an attribute or criteria list, usually filled out by an information specialist (expert centred approach). To evaluate these attributes – e.g. relevance of the subject, format etc. – a value is assigned to each criteria to allow a weighting. The second approach consists in establishing a questionnaire which is handed out to the target audience (user centred approach).

The users do some exercises to evaluate a resource or a system and to respond to the questionnaire. It is also possible to combine both approaches: A questionnaire containing a list of attributes is handed out to users (and not to experts) who weight the criteria.

This combination was used in the context of ACCEPT (Analyse du Comportement du Client – Evaluation des Prestations de Téléchargement), a sub-project of the E-lib.ch-initiative which consists in developing a Swiss electronic library. The objective of ACCEPT is to ensure the aspects of usefulness and usability within E-lib.ch.

In this context, a survey was conducted in collaboration with the Faculty libraries of the University of Geneva.

2 Methodology

The survey by online questionnaire was conducted between December 7 to 31 2009. Five departments of the University of Geneva were chosen: humanities, medicine, psychology and educational science, the school of translation and interpreting, as well as the institute for teacher-training. The return rate was around 8% (655 completed questionnaires).

2.1 Personas

The concept of personas consists in creating human stereotypes of a target public. Each persona has a name and specific characteristics – like attitudes, goals, skills and environment. As a persona should be as realistic as possible, some fictional details are added to make it more “human”. The idea is to create for each user group a stereotype, so that the system is developed based on users’ needs (Machate 2003).

However, a persona is not just a listing of data; it’s a factsheet containing a photo and personal details: name, age, hobbies, professional experience etc. There are usually between four and six personas for a system.

2.2 Using Facebook – how to proceed

To find more personal details for personas, social network profiles can be studied. We consider Facebook as most appropriate since it is used largely by students. This social platform is therefore very useful to find typical forenames, activities and interests for your personas.

A Facebook profile allows searching groups (in our case and among others: “Université de Genève”, “Faculté de lettres”, “Département d’histoire générale” etc.). Joining a group gives access to the member’s list and the different profiles. Private information is often only available if you’re a friend of a person. However, some people have a more “public” profile and it’s possible to get information about activities, study fields, books and movies people like. Once enough data “collected”, they can be rearranged to create the personas and combined with photos labeled for reuse.

3 Results

The survey results were combined in different reports for the University of Geneva. Based on these diagrams, three to four personas were created for each department: a bachelor persona, a master persona, a teacher persona and a researcher persona. These last two personas were sometimes taken together when their responses were similar or when there weren’t enough responses.

We’ll just present one persona, with usefulness aspects marked in italic. Françoise is professor in educational science. She’s 45, married and has a 10 years old daughter. She loves New York and goes regularly to the theatre or opera. She plays piano. Françoise prefers the *electronic version* of a journal because it’s accessible anytime and anywhere. It can be saved on a computer, searched by keywords; it’s handier and more ecological. She’d like the library to acquire more *journal backfiles*, so that she can access the archive of a journal online. She consults the electronic resources almost daily. She’s rather satisfied with the communication about the electronic resources. The *format* of a resource isn’t extremely important. However, *level of detail* and *up-to-dateness* are very important for her work. She *spends a lot of time to find a specific resource* (figure 2).

Françoise – Professorin in Psychologie und Erziehungswissenschaften

„Ich nutze das Angebot der Bibliotheken sehr häufig und verbringe viel Zeit bei der Literaturrecherche.“

Persönliche Informationen

- Alter: 45
- Studiengang: Erziehungswissenschaften
- Wohnort: Versoix
- Hobbies: Theater, Oper, New York, Chormitglied
Piano, meine 10-jährige Tochter
- Lieblings-Zeitschrift: Géo

Profil

Françoise bevorzugt die elektronische Version einer Ressource, denn der Zugang ist einfacher, sie kann die Dokumente speichern und direkt am Computer bearbeiten sowie zuhause oder im Büro arbeiten. Sie findet die Suchfunktionen (Volltextsuche) und das Format praktisch. Ausserdem kann sie die Daten in ein Bibliografieverwaltungssystem wie Zotero übernehmen oder sie per Email an Kollegen oder Studenten schicken. Und es ist ökologischer.

Sie konsultiert die Ressourcen sowohl in der Uni als auch zuhause, doch vor allem in der Uni. Sie nutzt die Ressourcen sehr häufig, also mehrmals pro Woche. Sie nutzt vor allem die Bibliothekswebseite und Suchmaschinen, um auf die Quellen zuzugreifen. Oft benutzt sie auch Kataloge.

Françoise fände es gut, wenn die Bibliothek über mehr Backfiles für Zeitschriften verfügen würde, denn die Archive sind für sie wichtig. Gegen mehr E-Books hätte sie auch nichts. Wenn eine Ressource nicht online verfügbar ist, konsultiert sie die Printversion oder nutzt den interbibliothekarischen Leihverkehr. Manchmal kauft sie den Artikel auch online oder bittet Kollegen anderer Universitäten, ihn zu besorgen.

Sie ist zufrieden mit der Kommunikation über die elektronischen Ressourcen und den kommunizierten Informationen. Als Informationsmittel bevorzugt sie ganz klar den Newsletter, doch sie fände es auch gut, News und Mitteilungen per RSS-Feed zu erhalten oder im Uni-Magazin zu finden.

Für Françoise ist das Format wichtig, der Zugriff auf den Volltext und die Aktualität sind sehr wichtig. Sie wendet viel Zeit auf für die Literatursuche.

Sie besitzt einen Laptop und einen Desktop-Computer. Sie hat sich kürzlich ein iPhone gekauft. Dieses nutzt sie für den Internetzugang und die Terminplanung, jedoch nur sehr selten für die Konsultation von pädagogischen Materialien. Eine Kompatibilität der Ressourcen mit dem iPhone fände sie gut.

Bedürfnisse und Wünsche

- mehr Backfiles
- Informationen via Newsletter, RSS-Feeds und Uni-Magazin
- Kompatibilität der Ressourcen mit dem iPhone

Figure 2 Persona “Françoise”

4 Conclusions

Personas are an easy way to represent user groups and their needs. They help to create user-centered services and products by understanding their way of acting and searching. Furthermore, creating personas makes work more interesting. Besides the empirical data collected by survey or interviews, you need creativity to portray a human persona: “If I were a master student in general history, what would be my name, my hobbies and my needs?” Social networks provide the basic elements for this creative process.

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